

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Six-Year Survival Rate Of Children With Systemic Lupus Erythematosus At Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital

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Abstract

Six-Year Survival Rate of Children With Systemic Lupus Erythematosus At Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital: This was a descriptive retrospective study. The aim of this study was to give informations about the outcome of children with SLE in Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital. This study exposed characteristics of the samples including age, clinical manifestations, laboratory results and complications. This study used medical record data of childhood SLE patients since 2014 to 2020. From these medical records, 45 patients were selected. There were 40 female and 5 male samples. The most age grup in female group was 10-15 years (67%) whereas male group had 40% in each < 10 years age group and ≥ 16 years age group. The most frequent clinical finding found in female was arthritis (47%), whereas in male patients malar rash (40%) was the most common. 90% female patients showed positive proteinuria and 100% male patients showed positive proteinuria. Lupus nephritis cases were found in 77% female samples and 80% male samples. Complications involving the kidneys in the form of CKD stage V were only found in 5% of the female samples. Based on the results of kidney biopsy, the most frequent class of lupus nephritis was class IV at 56%. For the outcome of the data obtained, 30% female samples died and none of the male samples died. Results from this study were the same as the previous studies which showed that childhood SLE was more common in female patients, with higher rate of complication and death cases.

Keywords: Systemic Lupus Erythematosus; SLE; Six-Year Survival Rate

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